

Nursing And Strengthening Of Positive Mental Health: A Review Of Women Victims Of Psychological Violence

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Abstract

A documentary review was carried out on the production and publication of research papers concerning the study of the variables of the role of nursing in strengthening positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence. The purpose of the bibliometric analysis proposed in this document was to know the main characteristics of the volume of publications registered in the Scopus database during the period 2016-2021, achieving the identification of 103 publications. The information provided by the said platform was organized by employing tables and figures categorizing the information by Year of Publication, Country of Origin, Area of Knowledge and Type of Publication. Once these characteristics were described, the position of different authors regarding the proposed topic was referenced through qualitative analysis. Among the main findings of this research, it is found that the United States, with 25 publications, was the Latin American country with the highest scientific production registered in the name of authors affiliated with institutions of that country. The area of knowledge that made the greatest contribution to the construction of bibliographic material referring to the study of the role of nursing in strengthening positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence was nursing with 58 published documents, and the type of publication that was most used during the period indicated above was the journal article, representing 83% of the total scientific production.

Keywords: Nursing, Psychological Violence, mental health.

1. Introduction

Psychological violence is the concept that is attributed to actions that affect the internal resources of people, usually occurring when there is no linear link, that is when there is a disadvantage compared to the other. This type of violence does not consist of affectations at

a physical level but at an emotional level, so actions such as humiliation and mockery are classified as violent. According to statistics, this violence is more common when the victim is a woman due to the gender roles that society has imposed. On the other hand, nursing is a profession with a very predominant human component since it covers the care and

prevention of diseases, which happens in all environments, so it is not limited to physical ailments but also affects mental health, so nursing plays an important role in the identification of behaviors in which there is psychological violence in the environment where the patient develops.

Mental health is increasingly taken into account when talking about the general welfare of the individual, so the competencies in nursing are being updated to cut to what society determines as integrity. Nursing is the main filter that helps determine the steps to follow to safeguard the general welfare of women, so it is important to educate on gender violence in the nursing academy to have the skills that facilitate professionals to provide care from the identification of the problem to the company in the recovery process. For this reason, the role of nursing in these processes is of utmost importance, since it is in charge of integral wellbeing and must take into account the emotional affectations and how these affect the quality of life of patients and the emotional relationships they present. For this reason, safeguarding mental health is as important as safeguarding physical health, and since nursing is a profession in which the main pillar is integral care, it plays an important role in the identification, prevention and treatment

necessary when encountering a patient, in this specific case a woman, who shows signs of suffering psychological violence.

2. General Objective

To analyze from a bibliometric and bibliographic perspective, the production of research papers on the variable the role of nursing in strengthening positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence during the period 2016-2021.

Methodology

Quantitative analysis of the information provided by Scopus is performed under a bibliometric approach to the scientific production regarding the study of the role of nursing in strengthening positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence. Likewise, it is analyzed from a qualitative perspective, with examples of some research works published in the area of the study mentioned above from a bibliographic approach to describe the position of different authors on the proposed topic.

The search is performed through the tool provided by Scopus and the parameters referenced in Figure 1 are established.

3.1 Methodological design

Figure 1. Methodological design.

Source: Own elaboration

As shown in Figure 2, the keywords most used in research related to the role of nursing in strengthening positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence are Woman, Psychology and nursing, which refer to psychological violence, which is currently more common among women, All this due to behavioral patterns that society has adopted as roles to be followed, so it is determined that psychological violence should be treated as urgently as physical health, since it affects the emotional well-being of the being, causing damage to the inner resources being more difficult to identify. Hence the importance of nursing in this process, since to identify it, it is necessary to be aware of small actions that can be determined as a risk factor. Nursing, being a profession dedicated to integral care, must be trained from the academy with the knowledge that allows it to develop skills that facilitate the

identification and treatment of these people to guarantee their integral well-being. On the other hand, there are keywords such as domestic violence, violence at work and mental disorders which are the main sources of psychological violence; usually, this type of violence occurs in power relationships that through mockery or humiliation damage the mental health of the person. For this reason, nursing is of great importance since having direct contact with patients can determine if a person is being a victim of psychological violence.

4.2 Distribution of scientific production by year of publication.

Figure 3 shows how the scientific production is distributed according to the year of publication, taking into account that the period from 2017 to 2021 is taken.

Figure 3. Distribution of scientific production by year of publication.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

The year 2020 presents the highest number of publications related to the variables under study with 25 papers, among which is the document entitled “Experiences of psychiatric

nurses caring for patients with physical and psychological violence: a phenomenological study” (Sim et al., 2020). This document aims to understand and interpret the physical and

psychological experiences and the positive and negative aspects associated with the nursing practices of patients with anger and aggressive behavior. This study is conducted in the analysis of the behavior of 12 nurses within which it was found that it is necessary to conduct more frequent training to nurses on how to treat this type of patient, it is also necessary to develop programs, intervention studies and improvement of the work environment that allow the nursing management in these cases to be optimal and go according to what is requested for the care of patients.

In second place is the year 2021, with 20 documents registered in Scopus related to the role of nursing in strengthening positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence, within these documents we can find “Unheard voices: Perceptions of women with mental illness

about nurses who routinely screen for domestic violence: a qualitative analysis” (Poreddi et al., 2021). This document aims to analyze the experiences of violence of 20 women and their opinion about the systematic detection of domestic violence by nursing professionals in mental health care settings, through this study it was achieved that women understood the situations that were defined as abuse, its implications and finally the disclosures of abusive actions. In this process, it was concluded that these women were experiencing more than one form of violence, and most of the participants supported routine detection by nursing professionals, concluding the importance of nursing in identifying patterns of behaviors that can determine that a woman is being a victim of physical and psychological violence.

4.3 Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of scientific production according to the nationality of the authors.

Figure 4. Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

The United States is the country with the highest scientific production in the period 2016-2021 with 25 papers within which is the title “The role of interpersonal style in aggression and its containment in a forensic mental health setting: a correlational and pseudo-prospective study of patients and nursing staff” (Jalil et al., 2020). The main objective of this paper was to determine the roles of anger and interpersonal style among mental health nurses and between nurses and patients in the occurrence of aggression and its containment, identifying how the dominant interpersonal style and self-reported anger affected this relationship between patients and nurses. This led to the conclusion that staff education and training programs should emphasize the importance of interpersonal styles that could help promote and enhance

positive interactions and a more active role for nurses in mental health processes for people suffering from psychological violence.

At this point, it should be noted that the production of scientific publications, when classified by country of origin, presents a special characteristic and that is the collaboration between authors with different affiliations to both public and private institutions, and these institutions can be from the same country or of different nationalities so that the production of an article co-authored by different authors from different countries of origin allows each of the countries to add up as a unit in the overall publications. This is best explained in Figure 4, which shows the flow of collaborative work from different countries.

Figure 5. Co-citations between countries.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

As mentioned above, the United States is the country with the greatest contribution to research related to the variables under study,

where within its publications are comparative studies that allow determining the progress of nursing practices in helping to strengthen

positive mental health in the exercise of their functions, in second place we find Australia with 16 documents having collaborations with countries such as the United Kingdom and Brazil as a way to complement the information seen from different regions, within these documents is the one identified “Effectiveness of primary health care services in addressing the mental health needs of the minority refugee population in New Zealand” (Shrestha-Ranjit et al., 2017). This paper has as its main objective to examine the effectiveness of primary health care services in addressing the mental health needs of Bhutanese refugee women resettled in New Zealand. This study

was conducted by determining both the experiences of the Bhutanese women and that of the health care providers, aiming to determine the effectiveness of this service for mental health improvement. This paper concludes that there are inadequacies and limitations in addressing the mental health needs of Bhutanese refugee women in New Zealand, taking into account certain recommendations to make this process a little more optimal and to address the identified deficiencies.

4.4 Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge

Figure 5 shows how the production of scientific publications is distributed according to the area of knowledge through which the different research methodologies are executed.

Figure 6. Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Nursing, due to the nature of the research, was the area of knowledge with the greatest influence at the time of conducting the research concerning the study of presenting 58 publications, within which is the document

with the title “Dealing with violence in mental health care settings: patient and staff member perspectives on de-escalation practices” (Berring et al., 2016). The main objective of this document is to conduct a multiple case

study exploring the de-escalation processes in threatening and violent situations according to the perspectives of patients and staff members, taking into account that this contributes to problem-solving and helps patients who have suffered from psychological violence to determine the actions that are not usually taken as violent but that have an impact on their mental health, which is why nursing, being the main contact, should be aware of these behaviors and the correct way to proceed.

In second place is medicine, where 50 documents were written following the guidelines of the topics related to that area. Among these documents is the title “Exposure to trauma in the workplace for forensic mental

health nurses: a scoping review” (Newman et al., 2021). The main objective of this document is to identify the key concepts related to the nature, scope and impact of trauma in the workplace for forensic mental health nurses. This process is carried out through a review of the literature, which resulted in all the effects that nurses in dealing with patients with mental illnesses presented being them the direct contact having physical and mental effects, even so, the necessary skills to deal with these patients keeping both patients and health professionals safe were evidenced.

4.5 Type of publication

Figure 7 shows how the bibliographic production is distributed according to the type of publication chosen by the authors.

Figure 7. Type of publication

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

As shown in Figure 7, within the different types of publications, 83% of the total number of documents identified through Phase 1 of the Methodological Design, correspond to journal

articles, among which is the one entitled “Experiences of family violence committed by family members with serious mental illness: a grounded theory”. (Paradis-Gagné et al.,

2020). This document investigates family violence perpetrated by a loved one with a serious mental illness by conducting surveys of 14 participants who had experienced this type of violence. This document deals with 5 main topics: medical-legal apparatus, the experience of violence, responsibility of the family towards the violent relative, exclusion and stigmatization, and suffering and resilience, showing the importance of nurses' actions in the resolution of these problems since these patients are usually admitted for physical problems that can also be derived from psychological violence, usually from a family member.

In second place are the reviews that represent 12% of the total number of documents registered in this study, within which is the document entitled "Nurses' perspectives on the factors that influence therapeutic relationships in secure inpatient forensic hospitals". (Stevenson & Taylor, 2020). This document determines the factors that influence the formation and maintenance of therapeutic relationships in forensic mental health settings, this research was conducted through a systematic review where the current literature was analyzed, concluding that the production of a policy statement that encourages forensic mental health nurses to be aware of intrapersonal influences on therapeutic relationships and the need to provide a safe and supportive clinical environment for these relationships to form.

5. Conclusions

Thanks to the bibliometric analysis carried out in this article, it is possible to determine that within the main characteristics in the volume of scientific production concerning the study of The role of nursing in strengthening positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence, it is established that the United States, was the country with the

highest number of reports through its institutions to Scopus with a total of 25 documents registered during the period 2016-2021. Due to the nature of the study, which seeks to determine how nursing influences the strengthening of mental health in patients suffering from psychological violence, it is established that Nursing was the area of knowledge with the greatest influence on the research identified, since 58 of the 103 publications related to the present analysis, actively participate with theories framed in that area of knowledge. Similarly, and following the nature of the study and the component of general well-being, medicine also played a fundamental role in the execution of 50 publications.

It should be noted that within the analysis presented regarding the position of different authors regarding the study on the topic proposed in this research, it can be concluded that nursing plays an important role in the identification of patterns that indicate that a person is being a victim of psychological violence, so it is important that from the professional training nurses are provided with the necessary tools to treat these patients, being very important the knowledge about gender violence and the kinds of violence, taking into account that all these affect the overall welfare of the person, and as this profession has a solid human component, it is called to help strengthen mental health, so a greater number of studies on this topic is needed since it is a fundamental aspect to determine integral health. However, it is hoped that through bibliographic and bibliometric reviews such as the one proposed in this document, the current state of the literature on the subject will be studied and that educators and the educational community will help in the generation of new knowledge in order to have more and more scientific material that determines the role of nursing in strengthening

positive mental health in women victims of psychological violence.

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